

From Theory to Harvest: Robust MPC Supervising Smart Greenhouse System

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Abstract—Advanced control methods play a crucial role in making greenhouse agriculture more energy-efficient and sustainable. This paper introduces an offset-free tube model predictive control (MPC) framework for the control of temperature and humidity in the laboratory smart greenhouse VESNA. The proposed approach effectively handles parametric uncertainties while maintaining optimal internal conditions for plant growth. The effective reference tracking of temperature and disturbance rejection for humidity are provided by the implemented robust MPC method. An extensive experimental analysis investigates different control setups considering various penalty matrices. Control performance was analyzed by evaluating control criteria, including steady-state offset, total energy consumption, and associated carbon footprint. This study demonstrates the potential of robust MPC for sustainable greenhouse control by providing offset-free control while minimizing energy consumption and carbon emissions.

Index Terms—Robust control, Model predictive control, Process control, IoT, Smart greenhouse.

I. INTRODUCTION

Sustainable production has made significant progress recently, driven by global climate changes. The ongoing urbanization process and excessive land exploitation also contribute to a gradual reduction in available arable land. Incorporating advanced control technologies, such as smart greenhouses, into agriculture significantly helps address these challenges. The effectiveness of control systems depends on various environmental factors, including temperature, humidity, carbon dioxide concentration, and photosynthetic radiation, which shape the target conditions. However, fluctuations in the environment and sensor inaccuracies introduce parametric uncertainties that can lead to incorrect control actions, potentially harming plant growth and overall yield, as demonstrated in [11]. In other words, if these uncertainties are not adequately addressed, the control system may either overreact or respond insufficiently, leading to energy inefficiencies or sub-optimal resource use. Therefore, it is crucial to consider parametric uncertainties in controller designs for greenhouses.

A commonly used approach is maintaining the predefined climate levels using two-position (relay) controllers or PID controllers. Despite many advantages, such as the low price of these controllers, they are insufficient for the effective control of complex dynamics inside the greenhouse with multiple inputs and multiple outputs, especially considering the interactions between these variables in the presence of

constraints [3]. On the other hand, robust MPC is an effective approach for multivariable control with constraints allowing to handle the uncertainties in the greenhouse model, see [12], and references therein.

In [1], the authors explore the impact of parametric uncertainty on the performance of greenhouse control systems, demonstrating how uncertainty can significantly affect crop yield, CO₂ demand, ventilation, and heating energy. Results presented in the paper indicate that robust model predictive control methods can increase control performance compared to standard controllers. In [10], a stochastic model predictive control (MPC) approach is proposed to address the challenges of parametric uncertainties in greenhouse climate control systems. By using model linearization and chance-constrained MPC, the approach improves robustness and computational efficiency in the presence of uncertainty. A particle swarm optimization (PSO)-based robust MPC approach has been proposed to handle these uncertainties effectively, demonstrating superior tracking performance and robustness compared to conventional MPC techniques [2]. In [6], a data-driven robust MPC framework using artificial neural networks has demonstrated improved prediction accuracy and energy efficiency compared to non-robust MPC methods.

The papers listed above show the advantages of using a robust MPC approach for supervising the greenhouse environment. However, they primarily focus on providing theoretical guarantees for control simulation. In this paper, a tube MPC is used to control the key environment variables in the laboratory smart greenhouse VESNA [8]. The paper aims to design and implement offset-free tube MPCs for two simultaneous control tasks, i.e., the reference tracking of temperature and the disturbance rejection of humidity inside the smart greenhouse. Several tunings of penalty matrices are extensively investigated from the point of view of the control performance with a particular emphasis on the environmental impact.

The paper's structure is as follows: Section II briefly presents the theoretical background for the tube MPC design. Section III introduces the construction of the smart greenhouse VESNA and the communication network between the greenhouse and the autonomous controller. Section IV provides an extensive analysis of the control performance of the investigated offset-free tube MPC control setups, and Section V summarizes the main contributions.

II. THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

A. Uncertain linear time-invariant system

Consider an uncertain linear time-invariant (ULTI) system described by:

$$x(t + T_s) = Ax(t) + Bu(t) + Ed(t), \quad (1)$$

where t is the discrete-time index determined by the sampling time T_s . In (1) $A \in \mathbb{R}^{n_x \times n_x}$ stands for system matrix, $B \in \mathbb{R}^{n_x \times n_u}$ is input matrix, with the pair (A, B) being stabilizable. Vectors $x \in \mathbb{R}^{n_x}$ and $u \in \mathbb{R}^{n_u}$ represent the system states and control inputs, respectively. $E \in \mathbb{R}^{n_x \times n_w}$ is a disturbance matrix and $d \in \mathbb{D} \subset \mathbb{R}^{n_w}$ is a bounded additive disturbance, such that \mathbb{D} is a compact set that includes the origin.

For the disturbance in the ULTI system (1) holds:

$$w = Ed, \quad w \in \mathbb{W}, \quad \mathbb{W} = \{w \in \mathbb{R}^{n_x} : \|w\|_\infty \leq w_{\max}\}, \quad (2)$$

where $w_{\max} = \|Ed\|_\infty$ is an upper bound for $\forall d \in \mathbb{D}$ such that $\mathbb{W} \supseteq E\mathbb{D}$ is the minimum hyper-box satisfying $\|w\|_\infty = w_{\max}$. The ULTI system (1) is assumed to be constrained by

$$x(t) \in \mathbb{X}, \quad u(t) \in \mathbb{U}, \quad \forall t \geq 0, \quad (3)$$

where $\mathbb{X} \in \mathbb{R}^{n_x}$ and $\mathbb{U} \in \mathbb{R}^{n_u}$ are compact sets with origin in their strict interiors.

B. Rigid tube MPC design

In the tube MPC design [7], the ‘‘tube’’ is introduced as the convex set $\mathbb{T} \subset \mathbb{R}^{n_x}$ representing the system perturbations. The ‘‘tube’’ is constructed as an invariant approximation of the minimal robust positively invariant set according to the algorithm described in [7]. The optimization problem of the tube MPC design is in the form:

$$\min_{\hat{u}_0, \dots, \hat{u}_{N-1}, \hat{x}_0, \dots, \hat{x}_N} \|\hat{x}_N\|_P^2 + \sum_{k=0}^{N-1} (\|\hat{x}_k\|_Q^2 + \|\hat{u}_k\|_R^2) \quad (4a)$$

$$\text{s.t. } x(t) - \hat{x}_0 \in \mathbb{T}, \quad (4b)$$

$$\hat{x}_{k+1} = A\hat{x}_k + B\hat{u}_k, \quad (4c)$$

$$\hat{x}_k \in \mathbb{X} \ominus \mathbb{T}, \quad \hat{u}_k \in \mathbb{U} \ominus K\mathbb{T}, \quad (4d)$$

$$\hat{x}_N \in \mathbb{X}_N, \quad (4e)$$

where \hat{x}_k and \hat{u}_k are the predicted states and inputs, respectively, for all $k = 1, \dots, N-1$, where N denotes the prediction horizon. Symbol \ominus in (4d) denotes the Pontryagin difference, K is gain of LQ-optimal controller and \mathbb{X}_N in (4e) is a terminal set. In the objective function (4a) $Q \in \mathbb{R}^{n_x \times n_x}$, $R \in \mathbb{R}^{n_u \times n_u}$ and $P \in \mathbb{R}^{n_x \times n_x}$ are penalty matrices chosen as $Q \succeq 0$, $R \succ 0$, and $P \succ 0$.

Subsequently, the control action $u(t)$ applied to the ULTI (1) is defined by the control law in form $\kappa : \mathbb{X}_F \rightarrow \mathbb{U}$:

$$\kappa(x(t)) = \hat{u}_0^* + K(x(t) - \hat{x}_0^*), \quad (5)$$

where \star indicates the solution to the optimization problem defined in (4) and $\mathbb{X}_F \subseteq \mathbb{R}^{n_x}$ represents the feasibility set of the initial condition \hat{x}_0 from (4).

Fig. 1: The smart greenhouse at Slovak University of Technology in Bratislava – sensors (green), actuators (blue), control unit (red).

III. SMART GREENHOUSE VESNA

The project VESNA (Versatile Simulator for Near-zero Emissions Agriculture)¹ contributes to addressing the challenges of climate change by developing and implementing the methods focused on maximizing efficient utilization of the fresh water and minimizing carbon footprint emission. These challenges lead to advocating and implementing smart solutions to enhance or maintain production quality while reducing its negative environmental impact. Tube MPC operates in a receding horizon fashion, i.e., at each control step, only the first control action is applied to the plant. Then, the optimization problem in (4) is repetitively solved subject to the current measurement as the system states the initial condition.

A. Construction

The current design of the smart greenhouse VESNA is depicted in Figure 1. VESNA is constructed as a cuboid of an aluminum frame with acrylic panels forming the greenhouse walls with dimensions of $0.5 \times 0.5 \times 1$ m. Custom-designed 3D parts, manufactured using a 3D printer, contribute to the strength and stability of the entire device. The front features doors, fans, and sensors on the side walls. The back wall houses control units and a power source for autonomous and remote control. The power source also contains a solar panel system to supply VESNA with renewable energy resources. Together with students, a custom printed circuit board was designed to integrate solar power and optimize battery management efficiently. Autonomous control consists of a microcontroller connected to carefully selected actuators and sensors.

B. Sensors and actuators

The VESNA greenhouse is equipped with various sensors to maintain optimal environmental conditions and ensure the

¹VESNA homepage: <https://vesna.uiam.sk>

Fig. 2: Scheme of communication between VESNA and remote autonomous controller.

growth and health of the plants. These sensors collect data on temperature, humidity, light intensity, carbon dioxide concentration, volatile organic compound (TVOC) concentration, and door-opening status. These data are utilized to control the greenhouse’s climate and irrigation systems.

VESNA also includes various actuators—such as a heater and air humidifier in the lower section, side-wall fans for ventilation, and ceiling-mounted growth LED strips—to enable real-time climate regulation alongside its sensor suite, ensuring efficient and sustainable conditions for crop production. Since temperature is particularly critical for plant growth, VESNA previously relied on a PID controller for control. However, this work replaces PID with a more advanced Model Predictive Controller (MPC), which handles multiple inputs and outputs.

C. Control setup

In Figure 2 is depicted the communication network between the smart greenhouse VESNA and the autonomous controller provided by Arduino IoT Cloud. On the site of the smart greenhouse, the ESP32 microcontroller collects from sensors data representing system outputs y and uploads them to the Arduino IoT Cloud. These data are later downloaded to the device using the VESNA CODE² toolbox [9]. VESNA CODE is a modular object-oriented framework developed in MATLAB programming environment allowing the implementation of advanced optimization-based autonomous control in the smart greenhouse VESNA.

The VESNA CODE handles the network communication between the Arduino IoT Cloud and the MATLAB.

The collected data are then used to obtain optimal control inputs using MPT+ [4] toolbox, which provides a user-friendly way to solve the optimization problem of rigid tube MPC in (4). Afterward, the control inputs are uploaded back to the remote cloud service. These data are subsequently downloaded by ESP32 and sent to the actuators.

IV. EXPERIMENTAL ANALYSIS

A. Offset-free tube MPC design

An experimental analysis is aimed at tube MPC control of the internal conditions of the smart greenhouse device. The controlled variables (CVs) are the temperature (T) and humidity (h). The associated manipulated variables (MVs) are the electric supplies to the heater and the humidifier, respectively. The corresponding actuators are located in the lower part of the smart greenhouse, see Figure 1.

Figure 3 shows the response of temperature and humidity on the step change in the humidifier from 0% to 25%. As can be observed in Figure 3, the profiles of the temperature (T) and humidity (h) inside the greenhouse are strongly interconnected. Therefore, the aim of this experimental analysis of the control performance is ensured by robust control, which provides the simultaneous reference tracking problem of temperature and the disturbance rejection of humidity.

To achieve offset-free control, the discrete-time state-space model for the temperature and humidity control in the greenhouse is augmented by an integral action member. Similar to the widely recognized LQR approach with integral action, the augmented state-space model can be expressed as

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{x}(k+1) &= \tilde{A}\tilde{x}(k) + \tilde{B}u(k) + \tilde{E}\tilde{d}(k), \\ y(k) &= \tilde{C}\tilde{x}(k). \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

where the augmented vector of the system states denoted as $\tilde{x} \in \mathbb{R}^{n_x}$, is consequently formulated in the following manner

$$\tilde{x}(k) = \begin{bmatrix} x(k) \\ x_i(k) \end{bmatrix}, \quad (7)$$

where $x(k) \in \mathbb{R}^{n_x}$ is a vector of state variables, i.e., the temperature and humidity in the deviation form, and $x_i(k) \in \mathbb{R}^{n_i}$ is an integral action member defined as an integral of a control

²VESNA CODE: <https://github.com/oravec-juraj/vesna/wiki/How-to-use-VESNA-CODE>

Fig. 3: Influence of step change in humidifier on temperature (upper figure) and humidity (lower figure).

error. Analogous, the matrices of the state-space model are augmented as follows

$$\tilde{A} = \begin{bmatrix} A & 0 \\ -T_s C & I \end{bmatrix}, \quad \tilde{B} = \begin{bmatrix} B \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}, \quad \tilde{C} = [C \ 0]. \quad (8)$$

Here, the original, non-augmented matrices of the discrete-time state-space model are

$$A = \begin{bmatrix} 794.2 & 0 \\ 0 & 774.7 \end{bmatrix} \times 10^{-3}, \quad B = \begin{bmatrix} 2.6 & 0 \\ 0 & 81.5 \end{bmatrix}, \times 10^{-3}$$

$$C = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix},$$

with the sampling time $T_s = 60$ s. The tube MPC design considers the constraints in (2) and (3) defined in the deviation form as follows

$$[-10, -20]^\top \leq x(t) \leq [10, 30]^\top, \quad (9)$$

$$[-50, -12.5]^\top \leq u(t) \leq [50, 12.5]^\top. \quad (10)$$

The constraints on the systems states correspond to the range of temperature within an interval $19^\circ\text{C} - 39^\circ\text{C}$, and the humidity in the range $5\% - 55\%$. The operating range of the heater power is in the interval $0\% - 100\%$, and the humidifier power is in the interval $0\% - 25\%$. Note that the integral action is considered to be unconstrained. Additionally, the bounds on the additive disturbance are determined in the form

$$[-0.5, -1, -0.1, -1]^\top \leq d(t) \leq [0.5, 1, 0.1, 1]^\top. \quad (11)$$

The penalty matrix of augmented system states consists of two parts, i.e., the partial matrix $Q_x \in \mathbb{R}^{n_x \times n_x}$ penalizing the system states $x(k)$, and the matrix $Q_i \in \mathbb{R}^{n_{x_i} \times n_{x_i}}$ as follows

$$Q = \begin{bmatrix} Q_x & 0 \\ 0 & Q_i \end{bmatrix}.$$

Throughout the experimental analysis, the set of penalty tuning matrices was extensively investigated. The considered control setups are summarized in Table I, where the subscript ‘‘T’’ corresponds to the tuning of the temperature control and the subscript ‘‘h’’ is associated with the tuning of the humidity stabilization. The main objective of the studied tuning was to ensure an offset-free reference tracking profile of the temperature while keeping the humidity close to its steady-state value. For the tube MPC design purposes, the prediction horizon length was set to $N = 50$ for all investigated setups.

TABLE I: Tuning of the penalty matrices.

Control setup	Q_T	Q_h	$Q_{i,T}$	$Q_{i,h}$	R_T	R_h
A	1 000	1	10 000	0.01	15	150
B	1 000	1	1 000	1	15	15
C	1 000	1	10 000	10	15	15
D	1 000	1	10 000	100	15	15
E	1 000	10	10 000	100	15	15

B. Results and discussion

The experimental results were generated by tube MPC control designed in MATLAB 2023b programming environment, using toolboxes MPT3, MPT+, YALMIP R20210331 [5] and solver Gurobi 10.0³. The constructed autonomous tube MPC controller was executed on CPU i5 2.3 GHz with 8

³Gurobi: <https://www.gurobi.com>

Fig. 4: Control performance of the temperature control with setups A – C: control setup A (blue solid), control setup B (yellow solid), control setup C (green solid), reference (red dashed), and input constraints (black dashed).

Fig. 5: Control performance of the humidity control with setups A – C: control setup A (blue solid), control setup B (yellow solid), control setup C (green solid), steady-state value (red dashed), δ -surrounding (brown dotted) and input constraints (black dashed).

Fig. 6: Control performance of the temperature control with setups D and E: Control setup D (blue solid), Control setup E (purple solid), reference (red dashed), and input constraints (black dashed).

GB RAM, and the remote communication with the smart greenhouse was handled via WiFi using the `VESNA` CODE.

Figures 4, 6 depict the experimentally collected control trajectories of the temperature (T) in the greenhouse for the implemented setups A–C and D–E, respectively, see Table I. The upper figures depict the control profiles of the temperature, while the control inputs, i.e., the electric supply to the heater, are shown in the figures below. The control trajectories of the humidity (h) for the investigated control setups are shown in Figures 5, 7, where the upper figures show the trajectories of the humidity, and the lower figures present the corresponding control input, i.e., the electric supply into the humidifier.

Although the presented experimental results (Figures 4–7) do not exhibit constraint activity, additional measurements under more demanding operating conditions were conducted, where inputs frequently reached their respective limits leading to necessity of robust MPC in scenarios. Due to space constraints, these additional data are not included here. Control schemes such as LQR would risk violating the operational boundaries or failing to maintain robust performance in the face of uncertainties.

The control trajectories presented in Figure 4, 6 show that all the investigated control setups were able to perform offset-free reference tracking in temperature, considering the sensitivity of the temperature. The maximum offset, approximately 0.2°C , was achieved when the control setup D was used. This offset is negligible, given the the sensitivity of the temperature sensor and measurement noise. On the other hand, results of disturbance rejection control problem in Figures 5 and 7 show that control setups A (Figure 5, blue solid) and E (Figure 7, purple solid) were not able to preserve the humidity in the predefined δ -neighborhood ($\pm 1\%$) of the required value.

Fig. 7: Control performance of the humidity control with setups D and E: control setup D (blue solid), control setup E (purple solid), reference (red dashed), and input constraints (black dashed).

Consequently, it can be observed that the penalty factor of the integral part associated with the humidity, i.e., $Q_{i,h}$ in Table I, has a crucial impact on the control performance of the analyzed disturbance rejection control problem.

Tables II, III present the evaluated control performance criteria, including the settling time t_{reg} , defined as the time required for the control output to stabilize within the δ -neighborhood ($\pm 0.5^\circ\text{C}$ for temperature and $\pm 1\%$ for humidity), and the steady-state error $e(\infty)$. Moreover, a total energy consumption E was evaluated for both actuators as follows:

$$E = T_s \sum_{t=0}^{t_{\text{end}}} Pu(t), \quad (12)$$

where $T_s = 60\text{ s}$ is the sampling time, $u(t)$ represents the normalized control input, and P denotes the maximum electric power of the actuator, i.e., 40 W for the heater and 5.4 W for the humidifier). The term $(Pu(t))$ thus expresses the power consumption in Watts at each control step. Subsequently, the corresponding carbon footprint $m(\text{CO}_2)$ was estimated based on the carbon intensity of 147.4 g/kWh^4 in Slovakia for December 2024, i.e., the period during which the laboratory measurements were performed.

In terms of temperature settling time, setup A achieved the fastest response at 20 min, whereas setups B and E exhibited the slowest performance. Regarding humidity regulation, setup B performed best, as its trajectory remained entirely within the predefined δ -neighborhood of the required steady-state value. While steady-state errors in temperature control were negligible across all control setups, humidity control showed more significant variation. Setups A and E had the largest steady-state errors, whereas setup D achieved the best performance with $e(\infty) = 0.43\%$.

⁴Electricity Maps: <https://app.electricitymaps.com/map>

TABLE II: Control performance criteria of tube MPC: temperature reference tracking.

Control setup	$t_{\text{reg},T}$ [min]	$e(\infty)$ [°C]	E_T [kJ]	$m_T(\text{CO}_2)$ [g]
A	20	0.08	57.53	2.36
B	28	0.09	93.61	3.83
C	24	0.04	84.47	3.46
D	23	0.00	90.50	3.71
E	29	0.09	102.28	4.19

TABLE III: Control performance criteria of tube MPC: humidity disturbance rejection.

Control setup	$t_{\text{reg},h}$ [min]	$e(\infty)$ [%]	E_h [kJ]	$m_h(\text{CO}_2)$ [g]
A	-	2.31	10.28	0.42
B	0	0.82	8.85	0.36
C	4	0.53	8.58	0.35
D	4	0.43	8.31	0.34
E	-	1.45	9.80	0.4

From an energy efficiency perspective, setup A minimized heater energy consumption by reaching the temperature reference the fastest, thereby reducing control effort. On the other hand, setup E was the most energy-intensive, with the heater consumption reaching the value of 102.28 kJ. From the humidity point of view, all control setups performed comparably. For the disturbance rejection problem, all investigated control setups exhibited comparable energy consumption. Note, the humidifier's energy demand and the associated carbon footprint were approximately 5- to 11-times lower compared to those generated by the heater, as the humidity-related control penalties were intentionally tuned to be more conservative.

V. CONCLUSION

This paper investigated the implementation of the offset-free tube MPC for internal climate control of the smart greenhouse VESNA. The primary focus was given to the temperature reference tracking control and humidity disturbance rejection problem. Experimentally collected data confirmed that tube MPC effectively handles the external uncertainties, ensuring stable reference tracking. Among the evaluated control scenarios, control setup A achieved the fastest temperature control, whereas control setup D exhibited the lowest steady-state error in humidity control. Furthermore, energy consumption and carbon footprint evaluations show that tube MPC can optimize energy use, thus reducing environmental impact.

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